

THE EFFECTS OF DIDACTIC GAMES AND THE USE OF MODERN INTERACTIVE METHODS IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES TO PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS

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Annotation: This article provides ideas for increasing the activity of students in the learning process through the organization of lessons on the basis of didactic games and modern interactive methods, improving the effectiveness of education and achieving the intended goal.

Key words: didactic games, interactive methods, teacher, pedagogical skills, effective lessons, games, learning process.

The organization of effective lessons in the primary grades depends on the knowledge and pedagogical skills of the teacher. Each educator develops lesson plans for a specific purpose, that is to educate pupils to build their knowledge and skills. In organizing the lesson, attention should be paid to the age of the child. The need for children to play games an important role in their primary school years. Therefore, it is advisable to organize lessons using didactic games and modern interactive methods.

N.K.Krupskaya, well-known Soviet teacher, said that “Play is a need for a growing child’s body. In the game, the child develops physical strength, stiffer hands, clearer body flexible eyes, develops intelligence, ingenuity and initiative”.

In the process of play, the child gets acquainted with the world around him and acquires new knowledge. Didactic games that contribute to the developmental of the child at an early age. This is a game learning for kids of this age.

Today, modern interactive teaching methods are widely used in the educational process. Appropriate application of these techniques leads to an increase in the level of mastery of the learner. The advantage of this method is that the whole activity

encourages students to think independently, to prepare them for independent living. In order for the lesson process to be organized rationally, the pupils' interest in their activities, the adequacy of teaching materials, various games to explain its content, discussions, small group work, brainstorming, it is necessary to apply techniques such as problem solving and encourage the pupil to work independently.

Nowadays, learning foreign languages is becoming more and more important. Even taught in preschools. It is the teacher's responsibility to make the lesson fun and to allocate time correctly. For this purpose, we will consider a number of interesting games used in teaching foreign languages.

1."Chain" game. In this case, a topic is selected. And the pupils line up in a circle. A pupil says a word on the subject. The second continues by saying a word to the completed letter. For example, if an "animals" theme is selected, one pupil says the word "rabbit" and the other pupil says the word "tiger" and so on. Anyone who does not speak within 5 seconds during the game will be disqualified. At the end the remaining pupil is the winner and should be rewarded.

2."Venn diagram.

This game requires you to work on the basis of two small groups. Two topics are selected. For instance, "winter" and "summer". Members of both groups write the differences between winter and summer in the first circle, and the differences in summer in the second circle. They write the similarities between the two circles in the middle. In this process, which group writes faster and more information and evaluates the accuracy of their data. And they are encouraged

3.”Find your friend” game.

In this game the class is divided into two groups. The first group is given sentences. The answers are distributed to the second group. The first group member reads the sentence without standing. One of the members of second group reads the appropriate answer to the sentences. The pupil who asked the question explains whether the answer is correct or incorrect. This process is monitored and evaluated by the teacher. For example, if the sentence is a “white” word, its answer may be “it is color”.

4.” A game of working with red and green cards”

The teacher prepares red and green cards for each pupil according to the number of pupils and a questionnaire on the topic. The questionnaire included questions that could be answered in the form of “yes” or “no”. Pupils are taught that the red card affirmation means the negative meaning of the green card. Pupils respond to questions posed by the teacher based on showing cards that mean affirmation or denial. The teacher must evaluate and motivate the pupils. Otherwise, the children’s desire to win may be extinguished. Due to these modern methods, the pupils boredom, laziness in the classroom is prevented.

In conclusion, it should be noted that in the process of didactic games, pupils learn to strictly follow the rules of the game, forming such qualities as solidarity and agility. If the teacher uses modern methods in the organization of learning process, of course, the effectiveness of education will be achieved.

In addition, interactive methods and didactic games allow the child to realize his creative potential. Because here he writes, fantasizes, thinks, learns, the child’s vocabulary is enriched.

The list of used Literature:

- 1.<https://hozir.org>
- 2.<http://library.ziyonet.uz>